

David and Goliath: a palm weevil (*Rhynchophorus palmarum*) kills a Great-tailed Grackle (*Quiscalus mexicanus*) in Nicaragua

David y Goliat: un gorgojo de las palmas (*Rhynchophorus palmarum*) causa la muerte de un zanate (*Quiscalus mexicanus*) en Nicaragua

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ABSTRACT

An unusual case of predation reversal is reported in which an adult *Rhynchophorus palmarum* caused the death of an insectivorous bird, *Quiscalus mexicanus*, during an attempted predation event. The observation suggests that the combination of an exceptionally hardened exoskeleton and the active use of recurved tibial spines allowed the weevil to firmly anchor to the bird's neck, resulting in strangulation. This mechanical anti-predator mechanism has not been previously described and may represent a more widespread defensive strategy within the genus *Rhynchophorus*.

.Key words: Antipredation defense, Antipredator strategy, *Rhynchophorus*

RESUMEN

Se documenta un evento inusual de reversión de la depredación en el que un adulto de *Rhynchophorus palmarum* provocó la muerte de un ave insectívora, *Quiscalus mexicanus*, durante un intento de consumo. La observación sugiere que la combinación de un exoesqueleto altamente endurecido y el uso activo de espinas tibiales recurvadas permitió al gorgojo anclarse firmemente al cuello del ave, ocasionando su estrangulamiento. Este mecanismo defensivo mecánico no ha sido descrito previamente y podría representar una estrategia antipredatoria más generalizada dentro del género *Rhynchophorus*.

Palabras clave: estrategias anti depredadoras, *Rhynchophorus*,

INTRODUCTION

Predation events in which small or apparently defenseless organisms successfully kill much larger predators are uncommon but biologically significant, particularly when such outcomes result from mechanical rather than chemical defenses. While toxic prey overcoming larger predators has been well documented, cases involving unexpected physical strategies remain poorly understood and rarely reported.

Birds are among the most common predators of large insects, including beetles with robust exoskeletons. Several avian taxa, particularly corvids and allied groups, have been reported preying on palm weevils of the genus *Rhynchophorus* (Krishnakumar & Sudha, 2002; Faleiro, 2006; Lo Verde et al., 2008). However, existing literature does not describe difficulties, injuries, or fatal outcomes for avian predators consuming adult palm weevils.

Rhynchophorus palmarum is a large curculionid beetle widely recognized as a major pest of palm plantations. Its larvae destroy the apical meristem of palms and are consumed as a traditional food resource in several South American countries (Fig. 1A), indicating that the species is palatable and potentially attractive to vertebrate predators. Despite this, adult *Rhynchophorus* are rarely considered significant prey items, and reviews on palm weevil management do not identify predators of adults as an effective control factor (Al Dosari et al., 2016).

Here, I report a remarkable observation of a predation reversal involving *Rhynchophorus palmarum* and the Great-tailed Grackle *Quiscalus mexicanus*, in which the presumed prey fatally incapacitated the predator. This note documents the event and proposes a previously undescribed mechanical anti-predator strategy involving the tibial spines of the weevil.

DESCRIPTION OF THE EVENT

On 30 October 2003, in San Marcos, Nicaragua (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/38273886>), I observed a female Great-tailed Grackle *Quiscalus mexicanus* interacting with an adult palm weevil *Rhynchophorus palmarum* approximately 3.5 cm in length. *Quiscalus mexicanus* is a common, opportunistic, insectivorous bird measuring 35–45 cm in total length, with a beak approximately 3 cm long.

The bird initially attacked the weevil by pecking forcefully, apparently attempting to fracture the hard exoskeleton prior to ingestion, as is typical when handling large insect prey. Shortly thereafter, the weevil became firmly attached to the bird's neck region, immediately below the beak. The grackle attempted to dislodge the insect by scraping its head against the ground but soon exhibited increasing distress, including erratic movements, loss of coordination, and vigorous wing flapping.

After approximately one minute, the bird collapsed and died, with the weevil still tightly attached to the neck (Fig. 1b–d). Photographs taken immediately after the event show fresh blood at the base of the beak (Fig. 1b), which may have originated from internal injuries caused by the weevil's appendages, although damage by the insect's mouthparts cannot be ruled out. The weevil remained firmly attached for a considerable period after the bird ceased moving and was difficult to remove manually.

Figure 1. (A) *Rhynchophorus palmarum* larvae offered for consumption in a restaurant in Misahuallí, Ecuador, illustrating the species' widespread use as human food. (B) Ventral view of the interaction between the weevil and *Quiscalus mexicanus*, showing an asymmetric gripping posture. (C) Left lateral view of the middle leg, with the tibia inserted into the bird's tissue; note that the tarsal claw is not engaged and remains suspended. (D) Right lateral view showing the right leg inserted at the corner of the grackle's mouth, while the remaining legs are anchored to the cheek and neck region of the bird. / **Figura 1.** (A) Larvas de *Rhynchophorus palmarum* ofrecidas para consumo en un restaurante de Misahuallí, Ecuador, lo que ilustra el uso extendido de la especie como alimento humano. (B) Vista ventral de la interacción entre el gorgojo y *Quiscalus mexicanus*, mostrando una postura de agarre asimétrica. (C) Vista lateral izquierda de la pata media, con la tibia insertada en el tejido del ave; nótese que la uña tarsal no está en contacto y permanece suspendida. (D) Vista lateral derecha que muestra la pata derecha insertada en la comisura del pico del zanate, mientras que las patas restantes se encuentran ancladas en la mejilla y el cuello del ave.

RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

Experimental studies on other curculionid beetles support the importance of mechanical defenses in deterring vertebrate predators. Wang et al. (2018) demonstrated that lizards preying on *Pachyrhynchus* weevils rejected individuals whose exoskeleton resisted their bite, while consuming those with softer cuticles. Adult *Rhynchophorus palmarum* possess an exceptionally hard exoskeleton, a trait well known to entomologists due to the difficulty of pinning specimens without bending or blunting steel pins. This hardness likely represents a first line of defense against predation.

In addition to cuticular resistance, some weevils are known to employ death-feigning

behavior, which may further reduce predation pressure (Mazza et al., 2014). Nevertheless, neither strategy alone explains the fatal outcome observed in this event.

Closer inspection of the weevil revealed a pronounced tibial spine or spur on each of the six legs (Fig. 1e–g), in addition to the terminal clawed tarsi typical of beetles. When placed on a human hand, the weevil moved normally; however, tactile stimulation of the thorax triggered a defensive response in which the legs extended and then flexed at angles of approximately 120–140°. During this motion, the recurved tibial spines became actively engaged.

With the leg extended, the tibial spine lies parallel to the substrate; when the leg flexes, the spine progressively penetrates the contacted surface, replacing the grip of the tarsal claws and exerting increasing compressive force. The femur acts as a lever amplifying the force applied by the tibia, which is structurally stronger than the terminal claws due to its proximal position and lack of articulation vulnerable to rupture. The recurved tibial spine thus provides an exceptionally strong anchoring mechanism.

In the case documented here, this mechanism appears to have resulted in strangulation of the bird. Photographic evidence shows that in at least one middle leg, the tarsi were not engaged (Fig. 1b), while one leg was inserted directly into the oral cavity (Fig. 1d), possibly facilitating anchorage of the remaining legs around the neck. The presence of blood at the base of the beak may indicate internal damage caused by the tibial spines within the mouth, although this cannot be conclusively established.

Figure 2. (E) View of the right foreleg of *Rhynchophorus palmarum*, showing the tibial spine indicated by a blue arrow. (F) Right dorsal view showing the tibial spine of the middle leg in a protruding position. (G) Lateral view of the hind legs, in which shorter tibial spines are observed / **Figura 2.** (E) Vista de la pata anterior derecha de *Rhynchophorus palmarum*, mostrando la espina tibial señalada con una flecha azul. (F) Vista dorsal derecha evidenciando la espina tibial de la pata media en posición protruyente. (G) Vista lateral de las patas posteriores, en las que se observan espinas tibiales más cortas.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The observation reported here suggests that the death of the bird was not the result of chance but rather the culmination of multiple complementary anti-predator defenses, including a hardened exoskeleton and an active mechanical anchoring mechanism mediated by tibial spines. To my knowledge, this specific use of tibial spines as a means of lethal restraint has not been previously described in the literature.

Notably, similar tibial spines are present in all members of the genus *Rhynchophorus*

and in several other curculionid genera, suggesting that this defensive strategy may be more widespread than currently recognized. Further observations and experimental studies are needed to assess the prevalence and effectiveness of this mechanism in predator–prey interactions involving large beetles and vertebrate predators.

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